

Bianca Trovò, 164146

Master Student in Cognitive Science

Neuroscience, prof. Daniel Adams, 2013/2014

September 2015

Despite the brain's clear anatomical symmetry, it is known that some functions have an asymmetric organization. Using examples, discuss examples of well- and of poorly-supported functional brain asymmetries.

Summary

1. Introduction
2. The heritage of Sperry's studies
3. 'Human, all too human'?
 - 3.1. Why two brains are better than one
4. Lateralization in human brain
 - 4.1. Creativity, handedness and gender: a matter of side?
5. Conclusion

References

1. Introduction

In a Mercedes-Benz print campaign (fig. 1) of four years ago the brain hemispheres are depicted showing the contrast between the left side (rational, ordinary, schematic) and the right side (creative, free and passionate).

Fig.1“I am the left brain. I am a scientist. A mathematician. I love the familiar. I categorize. I am accurate. Linear. Analytical. Strategic. I am practical. Always in control. A master of words and language. Realistic. I calculate equations and play with numbers. I am order. I am logic. I know exactly who I am.” “I am the right brain. I am creativity. A free spirit. I am passion. Yearning. Sensuality. I am the sound of roaring laughter. I am taste. The feeling of sand beneath bare feet. I am movement. Vivid colors. I am the urge to paint on an empty canvas. I am boundless imagination. Art. Poetry. I sense. I feel. I am everything I wanted to be.”

This advertisement synthesizes very well a popular view for which ‘personality traits’ and ‘cognitive strategies’ are associated with a specific side of the brain, such that there are ‘left-brained’ and ‘right-brained’ people (Nielsen et al 2013; Corballis 2014).

This idea that our brain is divided in two complementary halves, one more logical-linguistic and the other more intuitive and emotional, arose with the discovery of Broca (1860’s) of the language area and the studies of Sperry (1960s) on split-brain patients.

The contributions of these works are undeniable but let at least two myths establish: that brain asymmetry is a ‘distinctive mark’ of being humans, since the left hemisphere was seen to be dominant for speech and language (Corballis 2014); and that some cognitive functions like language skills and creativity are totally lateralized on one single brain side.

In this essay I will review how studies from the last twenty years until now have tried to debunk this myth, showing that 1) lateralization is evolutionarily important for a lot of species and not only humans; 2) cognitive functions don’t seem to be localized in the brain in ‘specific areas’ in a global way but locally belong to spread networks involving both the left and right sides.

I will discuss well-supported studies on functional brain asymmetry of non-human animals (§ 3) and show instead how the topic regarding humans (§ 4) is still a source of debate.

2. The heritage of Sperry’s studies

The most prominent study about the different functional specialization of the right and left hemisphere of the brain is the one conducted by Roger Sperry and colleagues in the 60-70s on the so-called ‘split-brain’ subjects, epileptic patients whose corpus callosum (i.e. nerve fibers connecting the two hemispheres) was surgically cut off in order to prevent the spread of epileptic seizures from one hemisphere to the other.

The experimental set-up used by Sperry (fig. 2) consisted of a screen placed in front of the subject’s eyes with a table below to cover several objects from his/her visual field.

The task was to fixate on a cross in the middle of the screen on which words were

Fig. 2. Sperry's experimental setup.

[illustration from Hugdahl 2005]

shown either on the left or the right. Those words could match or not with the objects behind the table and the subject could tell this by touching them with the ipsilateral hand. The idea was that the information seen in the left hemisphere would pass to the right hemisphere and viceversa.

Surprisingly, when the subjects had to report what they had seen on the screen, if the words were projected in the left visual half-field, corresponding to the right hemisphere, they answered they had seen nothing. Instead, when the left hemisphere was elicited by the visual linguistic stimuli, they would normally report the word they saw. Interestingly, this dissociation was not present with the tactile modality, such that even with the left hand subjects were able to pick from the table the object matching with the word that they couldn't report having seen (Hugdahl 2005).

These findings were really striking since they confirmed that the two disconnected halves of the brain would act as 'two brains' not communicating with each other, with the left hemisphere specialized for the language and the right for non verbal

and emotional content (Corballis 2014).

This influential discovery ended up shaping the destiny of further research in psychology and neuropsychology for decades (Hugdahl 2005; Vallortigara 2005) leading to “speculation about the complementarity functions of the two sides of the brain (Corballis 2014).

3. ‘Human, all too human’?

Initially, specially due to the known lateralization of language, brain asymmetry was believed to be a unique human property (Corballis 2014) and most of the research for almost half a century focused just on human species (Vallortigara 2005).

However, in the past twenty years evidence has shown incontrovertibly that lateral biases are present among a lot of nonhuman species of vertebrates, fishes, amphibians, reptiles, birds and mammals (Vallortigara 2005).

In particular comparative studies made it possible to hypothesize that in the lateralized functions of the brain there is somehow an ancient evolutionary line that goes from other species to humans.

Findings reveal that several species of birds show a rightward bias “for prey catching and foraging responses” indicating that the left hemisphere “controls responses that require considered discrimination between stimuli and manipulation of objects” (Vallortigara 2005). The right side, instead, seems to control aggressive responses and intense emotions.

In general this common pattern of lateralization in vertebrates, apart from the already mentioned behaviors, include for the left brain side recognition of species-typical vocalizations (from birds to humans), attention to local cues, inhibition of aggressive behavior and discrimination plus manipulation of objects; for the right side expression of survival emotions, visuo-spatial analysis and attention to global features. These cogent similarities across species “strongly support the hypothesis of an early common origin of lateralization in vertebrates” (Vallortigara 2005).

A recent study by Chiandetti et al (2014) investigates how analytic and holistic encoding strategies are separated between the two hemispheres of the brain of the domestic chicks, with the former lying in the left hemisphere and the latter in the right hemisphere. Navon’s studies on the perceptual processing show how the global level of analysis precedes the local, an effect called ‘global precedence’ and that is seen in human subjects (Chiandetti 2014). However, for nonhuman species, no study that explores this lateralized process for hierarchical stimuli has been carried out before.

In the experiment chicks had to choose between two hierarchical stimuli, as shown

in fig. 3.

Fig. 3. “Chick within the apparatus and hierarchical stimuli”.

[Chiandetti 2014]

Results indicate that in all visual conditions the chicks show *local level preference* no matter the hemisphere in use, confirming evidence of an advantage of analytic perceptual organization in non-human species in similar tasks (Chiandetti 2014). And this with no general lack of ability to detect the global level, which in other studies was demonstrated to be recruited for navigation tasks where the right hemisphere was crucial (Vallortigara et al. 2004 in Chiandetti 2014).

3.1. Why two brains are better than one

The presence of functional asymmetry in such a widespread number of vertebrates raises the question of what kind of advantage animals might benefit from cerebral lateralization.

The most accepted hypothesis is that “lateralization could be one way of increasing the brain’s capacity to carry out simultaneous processing” (Vallortigara 2005). Evolutionarily speaking, the strategy of storing different functions in two hemispheres instead of duplicate them would “save on neuronal circuitry” and information would be processed faster, enhancing the performance of the animal. Evidences for this don’t come just from vertebrate animals, like chicks (commonly studied because the left and the right hemispheres of these animals, as well as of fishes, are greatly independent from each other), but have also been shown for invertebrates such as the fruit flies (Pascual et al. 2004 in Vallortigara 2005).

Nevertheless, it’s reasonable that to be an evolutionary advantage functional asymmetry must not be just an individual property but should exist at a *population level* (Vallortigara 2005). But if lateral biases in behavior are maintained in species as ‘evolutionary stable strategy’ (Maynard-Smith 1982 in Vallortigara 2005) leading to ‘directional asymmetry’, a relevant question might be, instead, how this can deal with the so-called *predictability of behavior*, a specific disadvantage that affects non

predator animals (Corballis 1998 in Vallortigara 2005). Indeed, if the prey shows this strong lateralization at the population level, “then the predator can learn quite easily that there is a bias in the population of these organisms and it can exploit this regularity in prey behavior”.

However, how could that be that natural selection didn't lead to individual asymmetry instead?

It's possible then that there are ‘social constraints’“that force individuals to align their asymmetries with those of the other individuals of the group”.

If this is so, then the ‘social tendency’ of species (i.e. the tendency to ‘school’, to be gregarious) should correlate with lateralization at the population level.

Studies carried on schooling fishes have already shown that this directional bias is not present in non-schooling species (Bisazza 2000 in Vallortigara 2005).

A more recent study (Rogers 2013) demonstrates in invertebrates a similar association between lateral biases and social behavior. Honeybees, known for a rich social behavior, display functional lateralization in the use of the antennae. Specifically, in bees from the same colony, there is a significant difference between the use of the left and right antenna for social interactions (latency to contact

Fig. 4. Latency of the bees to make first contact and total number of proboscis extension responses (PERs) [Rogers 2013]

and number of proboscis extension responses, as in feeding), while in bees from different colonies this difference was not significant -fig. 4. However, in the same colony dyads reaction times for the use of right antenna were faster and more in number for social behavior, but fewer for aggressive interactions (C-response), while in bees of different colonies there were more contacts for C-responses - fig. 5.

For the authors it follows that the right antenna “elevates explorative social interactions and suppresses aggressive social interactions between members of the same colony”, in line with all the previous findings.

Fig. 5. “C-responses and mandibulations (opening of the mandibles) in the 5-minute test period. LA refers to bees with only a left antenna (right antenna removed), RA to bees with only a right antenna and BA intact bees with both antennae”. [Rogers 2013]

4. Lateralization in humans

Studying brain lateralization in low vertebrate species and invertebrates has the advantage of providing a more controlled study. As we saw before, fishes and birds have two separate hemispheres that operate independently from each other for parallel stimuli, and, as animal models, chicks can be studied since the first days of birth. Fruitflies and honeybees have small brains with no more than 1 million neurons and it's possible to easily separate the cognitive functions that compete the right and the left hemisphere.

When it comes to study more complex organisms, like primates, nonetheless, the individual variations vs population variations become more evident.

At the beginning of this essay we mentioned the emphasis of studies on humans after Sperry experiment. The 'dychotomous division of functional competence' was taken as a general fact for many years by standard models of hemispheric asymmetry (Grabowska 1994).

However, it was soon evident that things were not so simple: results like the one obtained by Sperry and subsequent studies were possible on subjects with abnormal disconnection of the two hemispheres (Vallortigara 2005).

Indeed, later studies on normal subjects revealed the great individual variability beneath hemispheric asymmetry, showing how this 'changes with age' and 'depends on life experience' and gender (Grabowska 1994; see also Nikolaeva and Leutin 2006 for geographical variations in brain lateralization). Older and newer

studies assess the idea of a different functional lateralization of the brain due to gender (Grabowska 1994; Tomasi and Volkow 2012), where men show superiority in visuo-spatial tasks, while women in linguistic activities.

Considering this high asymmetry at individual level, it would be really hard to infer that functional asymmetry is a stable feature of human brain. Specially due to the fact that it's still unknown whether this is an innate property in the brain or progressively developed through experience (Grabowska 1994; Corballis 2014).

Some help on this side might come from large-scale studies on brain networks. If once studies would make massive use of clinical data, like from patients with unilateral brain damage, and invasive techniques such as Wada test, providing "assessment of frequency of localization of verbal and visual-spatial functions in the left and right hemispheres" (Grabowska 1994), in the last 15 years use of non-invasive neuroimaging techniques to study connectivity has changed the view in the field, addressing the same questions on normal subjects but on a bigger scale.

A recent neuroimaging study conducted by Nielsen and colleagues (2013) explores whether functional specialization is a 'global' or a 'local' property of brain network. To say it differently, in the idea of the authors, networks connections could be uniformly strong between the left and the right hemisphere (global property) or instead the network strength could be unbalanced more either to the left or to the right (local property).

To answer this question resting state fMRI scans are analyzed over 1011 subjects (males and females) between 7-29 years old.

Significantly lateralized networks are found. On the left, connections involving 9 hemispheric 'hubs' (Ndr. "brain regions that are involved in many lateralized

The main goal of this study was to shatter the popular faith that in some people a predominance of the functions of 'left brain' and 'right brain' does exist. However, an important weakness of the study is the fact that there are no behavioral data and information about the handedness of the subjects is missing. In this way the authors can't really advocate for a sound argument against a stronger recruitment of one hemisphere in spite of the other, for example examining if such a difference persists between left-handed people and right-handed people (see later).

4.1. Creativity, handedness, gender: a matter of side?

The most visible studied factor on brain lateralization is handedness (Grabowska 1994; Corballis 2014). In human like in primates hand preference could reflect the preferred hemisphere, but the topic is controversial (Vallortigara 2005).

In particular it is believed that left-handed in comparison to right-handed people recruit both hemispheres or right hemisphere for specific tasks (tool use) and skills, like language (Grabowska 1994).

From this point of view this question is intertwined with the role of right hemisphere which we mentioned through comparative studies at an evolutionist level.

The right hemisphere is, indeed, associated with visuo-spatial functions and 'mental imagery' and its greater activation observed in left-handed people gave rise to fascinating conjectures about left-handedness and creativity.

Still now the web is full of sites that show lists of famous left-handed people in the fields of arts, science, politics and sports, in virtue of their putative faculties of reasoning not analytically but through 'insights' (http://lefthand.wikia.com/wiki/Famous_left_handers) or of articles on magazines of shady scientificity (<http://www.focus.it/scienza/scienze/13-agosto-giornata-dell-orgoglio-mancino13082013-7844?gimg=40457&gpath=#img40457>) that dig up a myth from many already considered unfounded (Corballis 2014) but still fueled by renown scientists in the field (see works from prof. Chris McManus, from UCL, and recent claims by Dr Hannah Critchlow, from Cambridge, both stating a 'superiority' of left-handed people in creative tasks).

Recent studies (Schlegel 2013; Beaty 2015) have been trying to show that creativity can't be confined in the right side of the brain, but emerges from a widespread network each part of it engages for a different cognitive process.

The equipe of researches of Dartmouth sets an fMRI experiment involving the notion of 'mental workspace', referred as a "capacity to manipulate mental representations flexibly". Behind lies an old philosophical idea, that dates back to Descartes, that any kind of thought is a sort of 'vision of mind'. From Shepard and Metzler's work on mental rotation many other findings have supported the fact that 'mental representations' exist and elicit visual perception. The aim of the study is to see how patterns of activation of the regions change over time during mental manipulation of visual imageries (fig. 8).

Fig. 8.

UP. “Experimental design. (A) Parts could be constructed into 2×2 figures, and figures could be deconstructed into parts. (B) Participants performed four mental operations on stimuli: construct parts into figure, deconstruct figure into parts, maintain parts, or maintain figure. (C) The stimulus set of 100 abstract parts, ordered from simple to complex. (D) Example of figures. (E) Trial schematic”.

DOWN. “Eleven ROIs showing differential activity levels in manipulation and maintenance conditions. An additional occipital cortex ROI was defined anatomically. CERE, cerebellum; DLPFC, dorsolateral prefrontal cortex; FEF, frontal eye fields; FO, frontal operculum; MFC, medial frontal cortex; MTL, medial temporal lobe; OCC, occipital cortex; PCU, precuneus; PITC, posterior inferior temporal cortex; PPC, posterior parietal cortex; SEF, supplementary eye field; THA, thalamus”. [Schlegel 2013]

Multivariate pattern analysis indicates several areas activated during the task, consisting of occipital cortex, posterior parietal cortex (PPC), precuneus, posterior inferior temporal cortex, dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DLPFC), and frontal eye fields, *on both sides of the brain*.

This finding seems to really demystify the simplified conception of a polarity of functions in the brain.

Yet a questionable aspect of this study might be that creativity is reduced to a sort of process of mental imagery, which can hold for activities that require a more visual task like drawing, daydreaming, even some forms of mathematical abstraction, but not for linguistic and musical skills for example. Moreover, considering the pertinence that gender and handedness might have in brain lateralization and the putative interactions among them as factors, the authors should have a) checked for the number of male and female subjects, which is unbalanced with more men performing the task; b) reported if all the subjects were actually right-handed, as usual in experiments.

Beaty and colleagues (2015) propose, based on a growing interest of studies on the interactive role of ‘internal attention’ for imagination, the interplay of two antagonistic networks during the creative idea production: the default mode network (DMN) and the executive control network (ECN). The activation of the former correlates with cognitive processes that engage “internally-directed or self-generated thought” (“mind-wandering, future thinking, perspective taking, and mental simulation”), and is counterbalanced by the recruitment of the latter, whose functions are oriented towards “externally-directed attention” (“such as working memory, relational integration, response inhibition, and task-set switching”). The creative process is then the result of the combined “monitoring of external events and internal stream of consciousness”.

Subjects were required to generate creative uses for everyday objects (‘divergent thinking’); as a control task, they had to generate typical properties of everyday objects.

MVPA and graph theory analysis of the functional network associated with ‘divergent thinking’ reveal a network of brain regions in which information is transferred from one hemisphere to the other (fig. 9).

Fig. 9. “Nodes (ROIs from the whole-brain analysis) and edges (paths between the nodes) that were used to define the divergent thinking network”.

[Beaty et al. 2015]

Again, like in most of neuroimaging studies, left-handed participants were not included in the experiment. So, for the sake of understanding if a correlation between handedness and cognitive function does exist and involves a reversed lateralization of the brain, this kind of study is not helpful.

No surprise that lately scientists (Willems 2015) have been asking to account for left-handers, since their variation can be really informative of brain functioning of the whole human population, shedding light to a relevant topic such as brain lateralization.

As for gender, instead, apart from investigations that explicitly look for gender difference in brain lateralization (Tomasi and Volkow 2012), most of these studies don't consider it an important factor to test, leaving the debate open.

5. Conclusion

In this essay we focused on the two branches of studies about brain lateralization arisen after the landmark discovery by Sperry, one on animals and the other on humans.

As we could see from the body of literature about functional asymmetry, there is substantial agreement regarding the evolutionary line that links the differentiation of cognitive skills from one hemisphere to the other in a number of different species.

The same we cannot say about studies on humans, where two opposite theoretical frameworks (lateralization vs widespread networks) are underpinned by more or less compelling results.

Previous studies in literature support the idea of a continuity in functional brain organization from animals to humans and this belief is still attractive for scientists, maybe because of its unifying power.

Last investigations with the new tools provided by neuroimaging methods, instead, seem to question the previous paradigm of hemispheric asymmetry showing how human brain cognitive functions are more likely to be spread in networks involving all the cortex. However, these studies somehow start from the implicit assumption that some hardwired differences due to handedness might be present at population level causing variance to the data. So left-handers are excluded or not taken into account for the experiments. Somehow this way of proceeding doesn't exclude at all that some form of lateralization for cognitive functions exist.

At the same time gender is a factor whose influence for an eventual lateralization of functions is not fully understood or inquired (see for instance Nielsen 2013; Schlegel 2013; Beaty 2015).

There is no systematic study of when both factors (handedness and gender) are mixed (for example Tomasi and Volkow 2012 take resting state functional scans of 913 subjects from a database but don't mention if they were all right-handed or not) to assess "if effects of handedness also depends on subject's gender" (Grabowska 1994).

References

- Beaty, R. E., Benedek, M., Kaufman, S. B., Silvia, P. J. (2015), Default and Executive Network Coupling Supports Creative Idea Production. *Sci. Rep.* 5, 10964.
- Chiandetti, C., Pecchia, T., Patt, F., Vallortigara, G. (2014), Visual Hierarchical Processing and Lateralization of Cognitive Functions through Domestic Chicks' Eyes. *PLoS One.*, 9(1): e84435.
- Corballis, M.C. (2014), Left-brain, right-brain: fact and fantasies. *PLoS Biol*, 12 (1), e1001767.
- Grabowska, A. et al. (1994), Individual differences in the functional asymmetry of the human brain, *Acta Neurobiol., Exp.* 1994, 54, 155-162.
- Hugdahl, K. (2005), Symmetry and asymmetry in the human brain. *European Review*, 13 (2), 119–133.
- Nielsen, J.A., Zielinski, B.A., Ferguson, M.A., Lainhart, J.A., Anderson. J.S. (2013), An evaluation of the left-brain vs right-brain hypothesis with resting state functional connectivity magnetic resonance imaging. *PLoS ONE*, 8 (8), e71275.
- Nikolaeva, E. I and Leutin, N. P., (2006). A Role of Functional Brain Asymmetry in Human Adaptation. *Behavioral and Morphological Asymmetries in Vertebrates*, edited by Yegor B. Malashichev and A. Wallace Deckel. Landes Bioscience.
- Rogers, L. J., Rigosi, E., Frasnelli, E., Vallortigara, G. (2013). A right antenna for social behaviour in honeybees. *Scientific Reports*, 3, 2045.
- Schlegel, A., Kohler, P. J., Fogelson, S.V., Alexander, P., Konuthula, Dedeepya, Tse P. U. (2013). Network structure and dynamics of the mental workspace. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 110(40): 16277–16282.
- Tomasi, D. and Volkow, N. D. (2012). Laterality Patterns of Brain Functional Connectivity: Gender Effects. *Cerebral Cortex*, 22:1455–1454.
- Vallortigara, G., Rogers, L. (2005), Survival with an asymmetrical brain: Advantages and disadvantages of cerebral lateralization. *Behavioral And Brain Sciences*, 28, 575–633.

Willems, R. M., Van der Haegen, L., Fisher, S. E., Francks, C. (2015). On the other hand: including left-handers in cognitive neuroscience and neurogenetics. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 15, 193–201.